

Meta Mining Ontology Framework for Domain Data Processing

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Abstract—Extracting knowledge from real-life data through data mining is a complicated process. Meta-learning helps optimize algorithm parameters to improve the performance of data mining. And semantic meta mining helps build workflows based on knowledge models. This paper proposes a data mining ontology integration framework for adaptive data processing based on the concept of semantic meta mining. It allows building domain-oriented ontology for data mining tasks. The ontology helps to choose suitable solutions and formats of the processing process based on data characteristics and task requirements. For helping to process the data sets adaptively, an ontology merging method is presented for the application of the proposed ontology in various domains. As an example, this article presents the application of the proposed ontology and method on the domain of time series classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of big data, data analysis is everywhere. But the diversity of algorithms and the clutter of data make the knowledge discovery process very unfriendly to many non-computer professional researchers. Even for the data researchers, it is still challenging to find the best solutions for specific tasks quickly. An intuitive and easy-to-understand intelligent assistant is needed.

Today meta-learning is very popular since it uses machine learning (ML) algorithms to learn from ML experiments for obtaining the best algorithms and parameters. And Melanie Hilario proposed a new optimization solution: Semantic meta mining. It relies on extensive background knowledge concerning data mining (DM) itself.

In the field of semantic meta mining, it is necessary to have a suitable description framework to make clear the complex relationships between tasks, data, and algorithms at different stages in the data mining process. Ontology is a computer-understandable description language. Naturally, it has become a choice when building DM intelligent assistants for various application scenarios.

The existing DM ontologies are usually dedicated to expressing one or several stages of the DM process in detail.

This concentration on parts makes them lose the integrity of the description of the DM process.

The performance of DM algorithms in each category makes them suitable for dealing with specific data characteristics. However, these data characteristics are defined differently in different scenarios. The various constraints of data set characteristics in different domains to make it challenging to propose a general and applicable description ontology.

This article presents a meta mining ontology framework to build a domain-oriented ontology. The main contributions are as follows:

- Define the structure of domain-oriented ontology as the general core ontology for data processing by integrating existing DM ontologies. The ontology describes the knowledge of each stage of DM.
- Within the general core ontology, an "INPUT" ontology is proposed for the description of data characteristics and task requirements, which are the basis for selecting suitable algorithms.
- Propose an ontology merging method for the application of the domain-oriented ontology in various domains. The labels of data characteristics are defined both in general core ontology and domain ontology. Domain experts describe the specific definitions of characteristics in the domain ontologies. A domain-oriented core ontology is generated by merging general core ontology and the corresponding domain ontology.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the relevant background knowledge involved in this paper. Section 3 presents the meta mining ontology framework. Section 4 presents the ontology merging method. Section 5 presents the content of the domain-oriented ontology. Section 6 presents an application of the domain-oriented ontology for time series classification. Section 7 presents the main conclusion and points directions for future work.

II. BACKGROUND

A. *Meta-learning and semantic meta mining*

Meta-learning [1] is defined as the application of ML techniques to past ML experiments, and its purpose is to modify certain aspects of the learning process to improve the performance of the results. Traditional meta-learning treats the learning algorithm as a black box, correlating the observed performance of the output model with the characteristics of the input data. However, the internal characteristics of algorithms with the same input/output type may vary.

Semantic meta mining [2] mines DM metadata through querying DM expertise in the knowledge base. It is different from the general meta-learning:

- Meta-learning methods are data-driven. And semantic meta mining is based on related knowledge and internal relations. So, developers usually represent knowledge in the form of ontology.
- Meta-learning for algorithm or model selection mainly involves mapping the dataset attributes to the observed performance of the algorithm as a black box. The parameters are updated based on experimental results, and the internal mechanisms of the algorithms are not the determining factor. In contrast, semantic meta mining complements the data set description by in-depth analysis and characterization of the algorithm: the primary hypothesis of the algorithm, the optimization goals and strategies, and the structure and complexity of the generated models and patterns.
- Meta-learning focuses on the learning phase of data mining, that is, the performance of the generated model. But semantic meta mining is oriented towards the entire data mining process. Based on the characteristics of the data to be processed and the task requirements, it provides users with complete corresponding solutions.

Compared with the conventional way of selecting algorithms based on the intuition of researchers, the main advantages of semantic meta mining are:

- 1) Ontologies contain factual knowledge about real-world entities and the relations between them, which can be efficiently utilized in various natural language processing, information retrieval, and any data mining applications.
- 2) Ontologies can be used to help solve more particular problems in specific domains through the proposed ontology merging method.

According to the above analysis, the role of classical meta-learning and semantic meta mining are not conflicting. The learning goals of meta-learning are more detailed (such as the parameters of the algorithms). And semantic meta mining provides the appropriate algorithm selection and formulates the execution process. These suggestions are more general. Such semantic meta mining can usually also solve the cold start problem of meta-learning to ensure that the learning process is in the correct direction.

B. *CRISP-DM model*

To avoid meaningless operations in data analysis, it is necessary to have a structured framework to implement data mining effectively and correctly. A suitable DM process model is the basis for building DM ontologies. Today, there exist three common frameworks CRISP-DM [4], SEMMA [5], and KDD [3] to format the DM process.

The KDD model is the process of extracting the hidden knowledge according to databases. KDD requires relevant prior experience and a brief understanding of the application domain and goals. The KDD process model is iterative and interactive so that it is too complicated as the framework of ontology building.

The SEMMA (Sample, Explore, Modify, Model, and Access) is the data mining method developed by the SAS institute. It offers and allows understanding, organization, development, and maintenance of data mining projects. But it ignores the steps “Task understanding” and “Deployment,” which we are going to describe in the ontology.

CRISP-DM provides a uniform framework and guidelines for data miners. It consists of six phases or stages which are well structured and defined for ontology building as Fig. 1 shows.

Fig. 1. The phases of CRISP-DM

Based on the characteristics of several frameworks, the simplicity and completeness of CRISP-DM make it suitable for DM ontology building.

C. *Existing data mining ontologies*

Recently, many intelligent assistants have been developed to optimize the DM process. Comparative studies are discussed in [7], [8]. Many DM ontologies have also been designed to help users build DM processes.

Panov et al. [9], [10] proposed a data mining ontology OntoDM, which includes formal definitions of basic DM entities, such as DM tasks, DM algorithms, and DM implements. The definition is based on the proposal of a general data mining framework presented by Džeroski [11]. This ontology is one of the first depth and heavyweight ontologies used for data mining. But it is just used for the

description of DM knowledge, so the algorithm characteristics are not covered.

To allow the representation of structured mining data, Panov et al. developed a separate ontology module, named OntoDT, for representing the knowledge about data types [12]. OntoDT defines basic entities, such as datatype, properties of datatypes, specifications, characterizing operations, and a datatype taxonomy. But the problem in the application of ontoDT is that the underlying data information is not enough to help users choose the appropriate algorithm. The application of OntoDT in this article is to use it as an upper-level ontology to help domain experts describe the characteristics of the dataset.

Hilario et al. [13] present the data mining optimization framework (DMOP), which provides a unified conceptual framework for analyzing data mining tasks, algorithms, models, datasets, workflows, and performance metrics, as well as their relationships. As the authors of the concept of semantic meta mining, they use a broad set of customized special-purpose relations in DMOP. But DMOP only covers 3 phases of CRISP-DM. And the structure of the ontology is so complicated to be unfriendly to non-professional users.

In the existing ontologies, the CRISP-DM process, which is composed of the 6 phases, is the basic framework. As Fig. 2. shows, most ontologies only focus on specific phases (DMOP covers three phases that can be best automated: from data preparation to evaluation; OntoDM the last four phases; OntoDT only provides a general description of data types for the first phase).

Fig. 2. The comparison of DM ontology coverage

There are several other data mining ontologies currently existing, such as the Knowledge Discovery (KD) Ontology [14], the KDDONTO Ontology [15], the Data Mining Workflow (DMWF) Ontology [16], which are also based on similar ideas.

III. META MINING ONTOLOGY FRAMEWORK

The primary attributes of the data sets, which are described in OntoDT, couldn't be used for algorithm selection. The general characteristics of the data set and task requirements are the basis for algorithm selection. Data in different fields have different standards for defining characteristics. Fig. 3 presents the meta mining ontology framework.

Fig. 3. The meta mining ontology framework

We can't know the explicit values of the dataset attributes suitable for specific algorithms, but the corresponding data categories (i.e., characteristics) can be summarized from previous experiments. The attributes could be used as parameters to define the characteristics. We define OntoDT at the upper level as a common data attribute set.

In general, in core ontology, we enumerate the data characteristics in advance. Experts define these characteristics with their knowledge based on upper-level restrictions and import them into general core ontology. It means a core ontology for a specific domain is generated as a domain-oriented ontology.

Users can query directly on the ontology to get the DM process for specific tasks. According to the characteristics of the data to be processed and task requirements, users obtain suitable solutions. Since the solutions have pre-processors and post-processors, complete DM processes are generated.

IV. ONTOLOGY MERGING METHOD

Since we hope to assist in the phases of CRISP-DM: business understanding and data understanding, how to present the input content accurately and flexibly is the critical problem.

We propose a new method to describe the data set through merging related ontologies. In general core ontology, the data characteristics are described and linked to the corresponding algorithm properties by the relation "isSuitableFor." However, the concrete definitions of the data characteristics are different in different domains.

As Fig. 4. shows, the idea is to describe data characteristics definitions in corresponding domain ontologies. While dealing with a concrete task, we merge the general core ontology with corresponding domain ontology. Then we can obtain an ontology containing specific definitions and descriptions of data characteristics.

Fig. 4. Data representation through merging different domain ontologies

A. Ontology notations

An ontology is made up of a set of concepts (C), properties (P), property mappings (T), and relationships between the concepts (R) [6, 22].

- Let O define an ontology.
- Let C define the set of concepts in the ontology.
- Let P define the set of properties of the concepts.
- Let T define the set of property mappings, mapping properties to concepts.
- Let R define the set of relationships that relate one concept to another.

which is $O = \{C, P, T, R\}$.

Concepts are the nodes or objects that identify something that exists. Relationships are used to indicate a similarity between two concepts within an ontology. They can either link two concepts together or loop back and link to the same concept. Properties provide extra features used to identify the concept. The property mapping element is similar to a relationship element, but it links a property to a concept rather than one concept to another.

The merge process occurs in general core ontology O_g and domain ontology O_d . In general, core ontology, concepts C_{dm} and relationships P_{dm}, T_{dm}, R_{dm} in the field of data mining are described. The concepts C_g of data characteristics are also included as part of the algorithm performance description.

Which is $O_g = \{C_{dm}, C_g, P_{dm}, T_{dm}, R_{dm}\}$.

In the domain ontology O_d , domain experts define the concepts C_d ($C_d \subseteq C_g$) and specific descriptions (internal connections) P_d, T_d, R_d of the domain data characteristics according to the particular situation of the domain dataset.

Which is $O_d = \{C_d, P_d, T_d, R_d\}$.

B. Ontology merging

For the ontology merging technology, the problem of finding common points for merging is crucial [19, 20, 21]. Knowledge workers must ensure that as many merge points as possible are included in the original ontology to ensure a strong merge. And the ontologies to be merged are complete and valid at the beginning of the merge process.

In our ontology construction, general core ontology is a complete and valid ontology that has been created. The concepts in the domain ontology have been preset. The domain experts only need to specify the range and values of the data characteristics definitions and ensure that these values do not conflict.

The merging steps are as follows:

- 1) Check for consistency completeness of the initial ontologies O_g and O_d .
- 2) Check that there is at least one valid merging point C_d in both sets.
- 3) Merge O_g and O_d at each of the merge points C_d .
 - a) Replace the domain data characteristics name C_d in O_g with C_d in O_d .
 - b) Add the domain data characteristics definitions $\{P_{dm}, T_{dm}, R_{dm}\}$.
- 4) Generate the domain-oriented ontology $O_{gd} = \{C_{dm}, C_g, P_{dm}, P_d, T_{dm}, T_d, R_{dm}, R_d\}$.
- 5) Check for the validity of the new merged ontology O_{gd} .
- 6) Check for semantic completeness of the merged ontology O_{gd} .

It is worth noting that domain ontology and general core ontology describe distinct domains: data characteristics and algorithmic knowledge. Their only intersection is the conceptual names of the data characteristics, i.e., C_d , which are identified as the merging points.

Because O_g and O_d are highly independent, problems usually don't appear in completeness and validity checks.

V. DOMAIN-ORIENTED ONTOLOGY CONTENT

In the initialization phase, core ontology is a general ontology, including an "INPUT" ontology and some other existing DM ontologies (DMOP, OntoDT, OntoDM, and DMWF).

Domain ontology is built through defining the existing entities of data characteristics in general core ontology.

Then experts import domain knowledge in the form of domain ontology, and we merge the domain ontology and the general core ontology to obtain a core ontology for a specific domain, i.e., domain-oriented ontology (see Fig. 5.).

Fig. 5. The general structure of the domain-oriented ontology

A. INPUT ontology for data understanding and business understanding

We create “INPUT” ontology as the input interface for the user query. Its primary contents are:

- Define data characteristic entities corresponding to algorithmic characteristics.
- Describe the requirements of the DM task, that is, the output of the DM algorithm.
- Supplement the missing algorithm characteristics and measure characteristics in the existing DM ontologies.

INPUT ontology is the part directly associated with the user's queries. It makes the use of ontology more explicit. Users do not need to understand other internal structures of the ontology.

B. Data characteristic description in INPUT ontology

For building domain ontology, the critical point is to provide restrictions for the description of the domain ontology at the upper level. In the previous work, there is no suitable method to describe the data set in the form of ontology entities. In the general data type ontology OntoDT, the basic properties of the data set are defined. However, these

properties cannot directly influence the DM generation process. The selection of the DM algorithm is based on the data set characteristics and task requirements. However, the definitions of these characteristics are different in different fields.

Fig. 6. The definition of data characteristic “LargeTrainTSDataset”

To make the ontology adaptively present data sets in various domains, we use the OntoDT classes as parameters to specify the definition (value or range) of data characteristics in general core ontology. Domain experts describe domain knowledge or existing domain ontology in general core ontology, making it suitable for data analysis tasks in this domain. An example of the definition in the domain of time series classification (TSC) is shown in Fig. 6.

The suitable DM processes are obtained by querying the generated core ontology for a specific domain.

C. The integration of existing DM ontologies for other DM phases

INPUT ontology is also the core part of integrating existing DM ontologies. The integration operation is based on the purpose of generating suitable solutions and processes.

In the process of integration, to reduce the complexity of the ontology, we discarded contents that were useless for this purpose and restructured the structures. The main classes in the domain-oriented ontology are shown in Table I.

The reconstruction contents are as follows:

- OntoDT is fully retained as an upper-level restriction that defines the characteristics of the data.
- The class "Goals" in DMWF and class "DM-Task" in OntoDM are extracted for the description of task requirements.
- Although DMOP provides more than a hundred DM algorithms and their characteristics, we have reconstructed its structure. As components of the DM algorithms, the classes “Measure,” “Output,” “Evaluation,” and “DM Algorithm” itself are included in a new class “Process” so that it is more understandable for the users.
- OntoDM describes the last CRISP-DM phase, “Development.” The classes “DM Implementation” and “Parameter” in OntoDM are integrated for the possible parameters setting. And “DM Execution” presents where and how to execute the selected algorithms.

TABLE I. THE MAIN CLASSES IN THE DOMAIN-ORIENTED ONTOLOGY

Class	source	Annotation
Data Description	INPUT	Describes the dataset characteristics in the form of ontology entities. Domain experts define their value and ranges.
Task Requirement	INPUT	Describes the task requirements in the form of ontology entities.
Measure Characteristic	INPUT	Existing DM ontologies do not describe the performance of measures (i.e., distance functions). In the INPUT ontology, we describe and name it "MeasureCharacteristic."
Algorithm Characteristic	INPUT /DMOP	Describes the performance of DM algorithms, including tolerating some data set defects (such as Missing value, Noise value), suitable for some task requirements (such as two-class, multi-class).
Data Type	OntoDT	Provide basic data types that describe the characteristics of the data set (such as sample, label)
Goals	DMWF	Provide a description of the task requirements. It mainly focuses on the generalization of the types of output results.
DM-Tasks	OntoDM	Provide a description of the task requirements. It mainly focuses on the description of specific details of the task.
Data Characteristic	DMOP	Provided by DMOP, the names of the characteristic of the dataset.
DM Algorithm	DMOP	Describe all DM algorithms that have been designed to perform any of the DM tasks, such as feature selection, missing value imputation, or modeling (or induction).
Measure	DMOP	Describes the distance functions and similarity functions, which usually directly affect the performance of DM algorithms.
Output	DMOP	Describe the output models of the DM algorithms (such as decision tree structure, probability distribution structure).
Evaluation	DMOP	Describe the evaluation functions of the DM algorithms (such as external validity model function for clustering algorithms).
DM Implementation	OntoDM	Provide a DM algorithm implementation scheme and parameter settings
DM Execution	OntoDM	Provide executable solutions for DM algorithms (such as R, python package, Weka)
Parameter	OntoDM	Provide parameters for DM algorithms (such as distance threshold, number of clusters and variance threshold for K-means algorithm)

In order to build the logical structure of core ontology, the relevant properties are defined in Table II.

TABLE II. THE RELEVANT PROPERTIES IN THE DOMAIN-ORIENTED ONTOLOGY

Property	Domains	Ranges	Answering the competency questions
availableFor	INPUT	Characteristics	Given data characteristics or task requirements, which characteristics should the DM algorithms have so that they are suitable for?
suitableFor	INPUT	Characteristics	Given data characteristics or task requirements, which characteristics should the DM algorithms have so that they are available?
hasQuality	Process	Characteristics	Which characteristics does the given process have?
hasPreprocessor or hasPostprocessor hasOutput hasMeasure hasEvaluation	DM Algorithm	Process	Which processes do the DM algorithm have?
isConcretizedAs	DM Algorithm	DM Implementation	How can we implement the DM algorithm?
hasParameter	DM Implementation	Parameter	Which parameters should we set when we implement the DM algorithm?
isRealizedBy	DM Implementation	DM Execution	Where and how can we execute the DM algorithm?

VI. USAGE

As long as the structure of the ontologies is reasonable, they can be operated on the corresponding editing software, for instance, Protégé. Based on the relations presented in Table 2, users can query for suitable solutions with the following workflow.

A. General Workflow

The workflow of domain-oriented ontology for data analysis in a specific domain is as follow:

- 1) Based on the restrictions of OntoDT, domain experts define the characteristics of domain data in the form of ontology.
- 2) Merge the domain ontology and the general core ontology to obtain the core ontology for the specific domain.
- 3) Manually obtain task requirements and data sets and describe them in the form of ontology entities as the inputs.
- 4) Execute the selection process on this core ontology for a specific domain.
 - a) Input the entities of input-data description and task requirements. Based on the relation "suitableFor", obtain the characteristics which the solutions should have.
 - b) According to the relation "hasQuality," obtain the algorithms or measures which have suitable characteristics.

If the results are measures, obtain the algorithms according to the relation “hasMeasure.”

c) Choose the most suitable algorithms which meet the characteristics as many as possible. They are the selected solutions.

d) According to the relation “hasPre/Postprocessor,” obtain the entire DM process.

e) According to the relation “hasPart,” obtain the process of the selected solutions.

f) According to the relation “isConcretizedAs,” obtain the implementations and parameter variants.

g) According to the relation “isRealizedBy,” obtain the available executions

B. The application for time series classification

Domain-oriented ontology can be flexibly applied to the data analysis process in different fields. As an application example, we constructed an ontology oriented on solving the time series classification (TSC) tasks. The entities of TSC data characteristics have been named in “INPUT” ontology. For describing the TS datasets in the form of these entities, explicit definitions are needed.

Fig. 7. Merging TSC domain ontology with general core ontology

Expert knowledge of the definition of characteristics of TSC data comes from [17]. We define them in domain ontology, then merge them with the labels in “INPUT ontology” as the Fig. 7. shows. Then users can represent the TS datasets in the domain-oriented ontology.

The interaction between the users and domain-oriented ontology takes place on "INPUT" ontology. Users can describe the dataset and query the corresponding entities of data characteristics in the following form:

“TSDataset and hasTrainSize exactly 40 sample”

Then users can receive the corresponding entity “SmallTrainDataset”.

INPUT ontology allows formulating the tasks in the common form. For example, the query for suitable solutions is:

“Algorithm
and suitableFor some SmallTrainTSDataset
and suitableFor some LargeTestTSDataset
and suitableFor some LongTSDataset
and suitableFor some FewClassTSDataset
and suitableFor some ECGTSDataset”

Which the entities “SmallTrainTSDataset,” “LargeTestTSDataset,” “LongTSDataset,” and “ECGTSDataset” are characteristics of the data set and the entities “FewClassTSDataset” means the task requirement is a few classes.

As Fig. 8. shows, BOSS (Bag of SFA Symbols), COTE (Collection of Transformation E), EE (Elastic Ensemble), MSM_1NN (Move-Split-Merge) and ST (Shapelet Transform) are selected as the answer to this query since these algorithms are suitable for all the conditions. For more concrete examples, please refer to [18].

Fig. 8. An example of the query in the domain-oriented ontology

We used 45 available TSC algorithms to process the dataset, which has the example characteristics. A comparison of the accuracy of all algorithms is shown in Fig. 9. The selected algorithms have shown excellent performance. The average accuracy of selected algorithms (0.9364) is significantly better than the average accuracy of all algorithms (0.7660).

Fig. 9. A comparison of algorithm accuracy for the example dataset

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a meta mining ontology framework for domain data adaptive processing. It allows constructing the domain-oriented ontology through creating an "INPUT" ontology that describes the characteristics of the data and task requirements and reconstructing and integrating existing DM ontologies. The domain-oriented ontology can be used as an intelligent assistant for domain data mining. The basic usage has been presented in this paper.

We also propose an ontology merging method to solve the problem of describing domain-oriented data characteristics in the ontology. The data characteristics in the field of time series classification are described in the ontology by the proposed method.

Although, the ontology is focusing on building the foundation of data mining, it can be used by practitioners in real-world applications to optimize knowledge discovery processes by sequentially querying the suitable solutions based on specific task requirements and data characteristics. Meanwhile, domain-oriented ontology is intended to be extensible and will continue to be updated to reflect future advancements in using it for building high-quality data-analytical processes rapidly.

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